

A Distributed Approach to Extract High Utility Itemsets from XML Data

Authors : S. Kannimuthu, Dr. K. Premalatha S. Kannimuthu is with the Coimbatore Institute of Engineering and Technology, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India, (e-mail: kannimuthu.mer@gmail.com). K. Premalatha is with the Bannari Amman Institute of Technology, Erode, Tamilnadu, India, (e-mail: kpl_barath@yahoo.co.in).

Abstract : This paper investigates a new data mining capability that entails mining of High Utility Itemsets (HUI) in a distributed environment. Existing research in data mining deals with only presence or absence of an items and do not consider the semantic measures like weight or cost of the items. Thus, HUI mining algorithm has evolved. HUI mining is the one kind of utility mining concept, aims to identify itemsets whose utility satisfies a given threshold. Although, the approach of mining HUIs in a distributed environment and mining of the same from XML data have not explored yet. In this work, a novel approach is proposed to mine HUIs from the XML based data in a distributed environment. This work utilizes Service Oriented Computing (SOC) paradigm which provides Knowledge as a Service (KaaS). The interesting patterns are provided via the web services with the help of knowledge server to answer the queries of the consumers. The performance of the approach is evaluated on various databases using execution time and memory consumption.

Keywords : Data mining, Knowledge as a Service, service oriented computing, utility mining.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014